

Introduction

Anxiety as an emotional feature is evident in most of the behaviours exhibited by man. Anxiety is a general state of apprehension, or psychological fear (Wade and Tavris, 2012). Hilgard, Atkinson and Atkinson in Al-Khasawneh (2016) defined anxiety as a state of apprehension and fear, resulting from predicting a threatening situation or event. Anxiety has to do with an unpleasant emotion marked by worry, apprehension, dread and fear which we all experience at times, in different ways. Barlow (2002) saw it as a displeasing feeling of uneasiness, nervousness, apprehension, fear, concern or worry. According to Corey (2015) anxiety is a state of tension that motivates us to do something. In other words, anxiety is the result of a person's effort to survive and to maintain and assert his being. Corey (2015) asserted that anxiety could be normal or objective and neurotic. Normal or objective anxiety is a realistic response to perceived danger in the environment or an appropriate response to an event being faced while neurotic anxiety is the type of anxiety which results from an unconscious conflict within the individual whereby he is not aware of the reason for his anxiety. It is worthy of note that normal anxiety does not have to be repressed and can serve as a motivation to change while neurotic anxiety is usually out of proportion to its provoking situation.

Lenka and Kant (2012) opined that anxiety plays a vital role in human life, in that most individuals are victims of anxiety in different ways. In the academic setting for example, anxiety features prominently among students especially those in the secondary schools, and mostly during examinations. It is very common for some students to fall sick during tests or examinations, some lose their appetites, and some sweat copiously on their palms. Some individuals can experience dryness of the mouth and some cannot sleep while some others become very nervous, especially when they are not prepared for their examinations. Every individual can experience unpreparedness for his or her examinations. Several factors can make it possible for students to experience unpreparedness for a test or examination. Such factors include poor time management,

lack of study skills, insufficient preparation with test material, and teacher factor, etc. Heath (2012) stated that during the actual test, students will 'blank' out mentally, be unfocused and feel like there is not enough time. Sometimes too, when a student has prepared well enough for an examination, he or she experiences anxiety which manifests through symptoms that could be physical, cognitive or behavioural, before, during and after a test. Bensoussan (2012) stated that even students who do well in class work and home work can suffer from test anxiety and do poorly on tests. Students of all academic achievement levels suffer from academic anxiety (Dobson, 2012).

The exhibition of a little bit of anxiety among students who are preparing for examination is not a problem as such because it pushes them to prepare better. This view is supported by Donnelly (2009) who observed that a minimum level of anxiety can gainfully motivate people, helping them to be responsible and to live sustainably and prosperously. If the anxiety however, continues beyond a certain normal level, especially among students, it can affect performance in their examinations and is therefore, viewed as a problem. Akanbi (2013) believed that some degree of anxiety is required to succeed academically but as anxiety levels increase, it becomes disruptive and weakens academic performance. Javanbakht and Hadian (2014) asserted that students have the skills and knowledge to do very well in testing situations but their excessive anxiety impairs their performance. English language is one of the compulsory school subjects in primary and secondary schools in Nigeria and it is also the medium for communication and teaching. It is one of those subjects that students experience anxiety in at examination periods.

In Nigeria for instance, a minimum of credit pass in English language is required to secure admission in the universities. Even if one does not want to proceed to the university but wants to secure employment with his Senior Secondary School certificate, the person discovers that most employers of labour give preference to those who have done well in English language; a pointer to the importance

English language performance, especially with respect to gender dimensions in Nigeria. This study aims at filling this gap. Also, a downward trend in the English language performance of Students in the West African School Certificate Examination (WASCE) is highly observable, as reported by Olaoye (2015). Test anxiety could be a reason for this. Against this background therefore, this study set to investigate the influence of test anxiety on comprehension level of senior secondary school students in English language reading comprehension. Performance in reading comprehension in this study, served as the indicator for performance in English language as a subject.

Whenever the issue of performance in tests or examinations is discussed, the issue of anxiety also comes up. It is pertinent at this juncture to observe the importance of assessing children to determine their level of performance vis a vis their anxiety level. Dhanaka and Unuaje (2015) opined that academic assessment in the form of scores and grades earned in class work, assignments, tests, and examinations has over the years played an important role as a means of evaluating learners' performance. The importance of students' academic performance cannot be overemphasized. It reveals the potentials and the capabilities that are bottled up in the learners and so it is necessary to find out if it is in anyway affected by anxiety.

Studies have shown that anxiety leads to poor academic performance and under achievement, poor engagement in class, and school refusal. Reilly and Lewis (1991) asserted that anxiety plays a significant role in students' learning and academic performance. Owen, Stevenson, Hadwin, and Murpate (2013) stated that anxiety can

require communication or that involve potential peer or teacher evaluation and consequently miss the benefit of interactive learning experiences. Dobson (2012) stated that anxiety can lead to problems with reading comprehension in that when some students are so worried about failing an assignment or test, they cannot retrieve information or store new information. When one is worried, the capacity for other mental tasks gets depleted and so does the capacity for concentration on other academic problems and problem solving. Huberty (2012) found that as a student's academic performance suffers, the anxiety level related to certain academic tasks increases. According to Davis (2004) test anxiety decreases attention span, memory and concentration and then leads to low academic performance. Eysenck (2001) discovered that test anxiety creates irrelevant thoughts, preoccupations and decreased attention and concentration, and thus leads to academic difficulty. Needham (2006) citing Sanders (2001) observed that when attention and concentration are disturbed (probably by anxiety), memory is disrupted and the consequence is low academic achievement. The purpose of this study was to investigate the influence of test anxiety on English language reading comprehension of senior secondary students and to suggest ways of encouraging healthy levels of academic test anxiety.

This study is significant in that findings from it may provide useful information to students, teachers, and curriculum planners on academic anxiety and its influence on academic performance of students. Counsellors may find it useful as they guide students on how to perform better considering their diverse needs and background.

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were formulated to guide this investigation:

1. There is no significant relationship between the academic test anxiety scores of students and their reading comprehension scores.
2. There is no significant difference between the academic test anxiety scores of male and female students.
3. There is no significant difference in reading comprehension scores between students with high academic test anxiety and those with low academic test anxiety.

Method

The study is a descriptive field survey. The population consisted of the two hundred and twenty five SS3 students in Government Secondary School Gwarinpa, Abuja. Through a simple random sampling technique, two hundred students from the SS3 class of this secondary school were selected as sample for the study. The test anxiety questionnaire of Nist and Diehl (1990) and a reading comprehension test jointly designed by some experienced English language teachers served as the instruments for data collection. The test anxiety questionnaire was to elicit information on the academic test anxiety level of students while the reading comprehension test was to provide information on the students' comprehension which would serve as an index for academic performance. The test anxiety questionnaire comprises ten simple questions with each question having options that took the form of a 5-point Likert-like scale namely Never (1), Rarely (2), Sometimes (3), Often (4) Always (5). Each Participant's scores on all statements were added up. According to Nist and Diehl (1990) the scores range from 10 to 50, a score of (10-19) shows that one does not suffer from test anxiety while a person with an extremely low score (close to 10), may need a little more anxiety to be healthy, to keep one focused and to get his blood flowing during exams. Scores of 20 – 35 indicate that, although one exhibits some of the characteristics of test anxiety, the level of stress and tension is probably healthy. Scores over 35 point to the fact that one is

experiencing an unhealthy level of anxiety. For convenience therefore, anxiety scores of 10 to 35 were taken as low while scores above 35 were taken as high. The reading comprehension test consisted of two sections A and B. Section A was used to indicate demographic information such as age and sex, while section B consisted of ten items which tested the students' ability to comprehend information.

On the reliability of the Nist and Diehl's anxiety questionnaire, Heath (2012) stated that many colleges have used it on their students and found it valid and reliable. Banka and Hyland (2016) used the questionnaire and found it very reliable, with a Cronbach's alpha value of 0.86. To establish the reliability of the reading comprehension test jointly designed by some experienced English language teachers, a test – retest was done using Pearson Product Moment Coefficient which gave a value of 0.88 showing that the instrument is reliable.

The researchers visited the school under investigation to administer the Academic Test Anxiety questionnaire on the 200 senior secondary 3 students who were the respondents. To avoid faking, the students were asked not to write their names on the test anxiety questionnaires but to write the numbers assigned to them. With the assistance of the experienced English language teachers who designed the English comprehension test, the test was administered on the students and marked. Using the numbers assigned to the students, the test anxiety scores and the reading comprehension scores were collated, indicating whether the subjects were males or females. The data collected was analyzed using mean, standard deviation, correlation and t-test. The analysis of data was done in line with the hypotheses for the study.

Data Analysis/ Findings

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant relationship between the academic test anxiety scores of students and their reading comprehension scores. The result for the testing of this hypothesis is as shown on table 1 below.

Correlations

		academic test anxiety scores	reading comp. scores
academic test anxiety scores	Pearson Correlation	1	-.250**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	200	200
reading comp. scores	Pearson Correlation	-.250**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	200	200

**Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed), $r = -0.181$; $df = 199$

The result in table 1 shows a calculated correlation coefficient of -0.250 . It means that there is a significant negative correlation or an inverse correlation between the academic test anxiety scores and reading comprehension scores of students. Therefore, the null hypothesis 1 which states

that there is no significant relationship between the test anxiety scores of students and their reading comprehension achievement is rejected. It means that as the test anxiety score increases, the reading comprehension performance decreases.

Table2: Independent t-test result for the difference between academic test anxiety scores of male and female students.

2a Group Statistics

	Gender	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Anxiety	1(m)	110	29.3818	10.84755	1.03427
	2(f)	90	28.8333	11.89302	1.25363

		Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means				95% Confidence Interval of the Difference		
		F	Sig.	T	Df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	Lower	Upper
Anxiety	Equal variances assumed	.680	.411	.341	198	.734	.54848	1.61029	-2.62704	3.72401
	Equal variances not assumed			.337	182.393	.736	.54848	1.62521	-2.65815	3.75512

The result of analysis in table 2 shows that the calculated t-value of .341 was less than the critical t-value of 1.97 at 0.05 level of significance with 198 degree of freedom. This means that there is no significant difference between the academic anxiety scores of male and female students at 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, the null

hypothesis which says that there is no significant difference between the academic test anxiety scores of male and female students is accepted. The mean score for academic test anxiety for males is 29.3 with a standard deviation of 10.8 while that of the female students is 28.8 with a standard deviation of 11.8. This shows that even

though there is no significant difference, the male students scored slightly higher in academic test anxiety than the females.

Hypothesis 3: There is no significant difference in reading comprehension scores

between students with high academic test anxiety and those with low academic test anxiety. The result for the testing of this hypothesis is as shown on tables 3a and b below.

Table 3: Independent t-test result for the differences in reading comprehension scores of high and low academic test anxiety students.

3a. Group Statistics

	Group	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Comprehension	1(H)	66	17.6818		.56020
	2(L)	59	21.9831	7.80471	1.01609

3b. Independent Samples Test

		Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means				95% Confidence Interval of the Difference		
		F	Sig.	T	Df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	Lower	Upper
Comprehension	Equal variances assumed	21.858	.000	-3.812	123	.000	-4.30123	1.12845	-6.53494	-2.06753
	Equal variances not assumed			3.707	91.108	.000	-4.30123	1.16028	-6.60596	-1.99651

*Significant (P<.05); Critical t = 1.980; df 123

The result in table 3 shows that the p value of 0.000 is less than 0.05 meaning that there is a significant difference between the reading comprehension scores of high academic test anxiety students and low academic test anxiety students at 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, the null hypothesis which says that there is no significant difference between the reading comprehension scores of high academic test anxiety students and low academic test anxiety students is rejected. The mean score for reading comprehension scores for high academic test anxiety students is 17.6 while that of the low academic test anxiety students is 21.9. This shows that the difference is in favour of the low academic test anxiety students i.e., the low academic test anxiety students scored higher in reading comprehension than the high academic test anxiety students.

Discussion

The result of the study showed a significant negative correlation between the academic test anxiety scores of the students and their reading comprehension scores, meaning that as the academic anxiety levels of students increased, their reading comprehension reduced. Consequently, the null hypothesis 1 which stated that there is no significant relationship between the academic test anxiety scores and reading comprehension scores was rejected while the alternative was accepted. This result agrees with Singh (2009) and Rezazadeh and Tavakoli (2009) who independently concluded the existence of a significant negative correlation between academic achievement and academic anxiety. The results in table 2a and b showed that there was no significant difference between the academic test anxiety scores of male and female students which led to the

acceptance of null hypothesis 2. This is in line with the findings of Jain (2012) that there was no significant difference between the academic anxiety of boys and girls. However the mean scores showed that the male students had slightly higher anxiety than females and this disagrees with Ali, Awan, Batool, and Muhammad (2013) who found that female students had higher test anxiety than male students in English Language. The result in tables 3a and b showed a significant difference between the reading comprehension scores of high and low anxiety students. This shows that the performance of high academic anxiety students differs from the performance of those with lower academic anxiety. This agrees with the findings of Hamzah (2007) that school students with higher level of academic anxiety have lower academic performance while those with lower anxiety levels have higher academic performance.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of the study, it was concluded that students with high anxiety level perform poorly in reading comprehension text. This means that academic achievements of students can be affected by anxiety. Academic test anxiety scores of male and female students do not significantly differ but reading comprehension scores of high and low academic anxiety students differ. This means that low anxiety students' performance is better than that of higher academic anxiety students. The academic achievement of youths of every nation goes a long way to impact on its growth and development. Poor academic achievements hinder sustainable development hence; matters related to academic achievement should be treated with seriousness.

Recommendations

It is in mind that anxiety can negatively affect academic performance, the following recommendations are proffered:

- Teachers should be exposed to continuing professional development
- Guidance Counsellors should be equipped with

levels of anxiety should be sent to professionals to receive behavior therapy.

- Teachers should be observant enough while students are performing given tasks to note when they are becoming anxious so as to provide support and encouragement. They can do this through initiating a dialogue on anxiety through which they acknowledge their feelings and encourage their efforts.
- Teachers should endeavour to reward non-anxious behaviour while redirecting anxious ones. For instance if a child is complaining that he finds mathematics tasks difficult and dodges the mathematics class, the teacher can redirect his behaviour by giving him easier and more interesting tasks in mathematics and then gradually introduce him to the more tasking ones.
- Guidance Counsellors and teachers should plan programmes like 'study technology' to promote healthy anxiety levels. Students should be taught test preparation skills which help to boost their confidence.

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INFLUENCE OF ACADEMIC TEST ANXIETY ON THE READING COMPREHENSION OF STUDENTS OF GOVERNMENT SECONDARY SCHOOL GWARINPA, ABUJA, FEDERAL CAPITAL TERRITORY

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Abstract

This study is a descriptive field survey designed to investigate the influence of test anxiety on the reading comprehension of Senior Secondary III (SS3) students of Government Secondary School (GSS) Gwarinpa, Abuja, with a population of two hundred and twenty five. A sample of two hundred (200) students randomly selected from this population served as the study participants. Three hypotheses were formulated to guide this study. The test anxiety questionnaire by Nist and Diehl (1990) and the English Language reading comprehension exercise jointly set by some English Language teachers served as the instruments for data collection. Student t-test and Correlation analysis were the statistical tools for data analysis. Findings from this research revealed an inverse relationship (negative correlation) between the test anxiety of students and their reading comprehension and no significant difference between the anxiety scores of male and female students. There was also no significant difference between reading comprehension scores of high test anxiety students and low test anxiety students. The implication of this is that efforts should be geared by educational stakeholders towards helping students to reduce any abnormal level of anxiety which negatively affects academic performance. It was recommended among others that teachers should be exposed to continuous professional development during which they are equipped with strategies for detecting signs of anxiety and how to reduce it.

Keywords: *Academic Test anxiety, Reading Comprehension, Students.*